

TEACHING STUDENTS IN TECHNICAL UNIVERSITIES USE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES .

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Abstract: *in the process of teaching students with the help of digital technologies in higher technical educational institutions , it is possible to provide instructional manuals and methodological materials, the use of digital technologies in the educational process changes the teacher's attitude to his professional activity and students' learning regulates educational activities and the educational process between teachers and students.*

Key words: *technologies, educational process, program, student, educational material, opportunity, higher education, educational material, computer, video materials, visual material, independent work, technical training guide.*

Wide spread of electronic and multimedia educational tools in the world of high technologies is the basis for the development of modern engineering education, which opens up new perspectives for the use of digital resources in ensuring the availability, continuity and quality of education of digitization education, and for the training of technical specialists. digital educational resources using electronic and multimedia educational programs as a means of professional communication will have the opportunity to master technical sciences and increase students' interest in studying technical sciences [1], as well as a priority in higher vocational technical education Optimum education of teachers and students on the basis of the system by effectively using information technologies, i.e. methods, production processes and a set of hardware and software tools combined in a technological chain that provides information collection, processing, storage, transmission and display allows to organize interaction [2].

All electronic versions of the training courses will be based on a single technical topic with a test or assessment system, illustrations and glossaries.

In order to use information technologies [3]:

1. Development of the student's personality, preparation for independent production activities in the information society:

- development of constructive, algorithmic thinking due to the specific features of communication with a computer;

- development of creative thinking by reducing the share of reproductive activity;

- active use of demonstration materials and technical training manuals ;

- formation of information culture, ability to process information (using electronic spreadsheet processors) [4].

2. Realization of social order at the expense of informatization of modern society:

- preparing students for independent knowledge activities with the help of information technologies [5].

3. Motivation of the educational process :

- to increase the quality and efficiency of the educational process by introducing the possibilities of information technologies;

- identifying and using stimulation tools to activate cognitive activity [6].

It is advisable to use animation of individual elements, video supplements , taking into account that the topics being mastered in educational video presentations are shown in detail, the summarized information is divided into chapters and sections in the specified order [7].

Ensuring that the introduction of such information technologies into the educational process is justified in terms of quality, the use of these complexes in the professional training of future specialists will improve the quality of education , develop students ' creative abilities , enable them to think independently and allows

teaching to work with educational material . This helps them to improve continuously [8].

An important component of a professionally oriented environment for information and education in the practice of the educational process is a modular information and training system, which includes a software component of mastering the subject, which provides the student with information-searching. allows to implement and get to know information-reference activities in full [9].

One of the main components is electronic learning technologies that work as an integral tool for solving professional tasks through programmatic, methodological, informational and didactic support [10].

An important component of the professionally oriented environment for information and education in the practice of the educational process is the modular information and training system, which includes the software component of mastering the subject, which allows the student to perform information- searching . allows to increase and fully implement information and reference activities [11].

The main problems that arise in this case are:

- computerization for training course processing ;
- in the construction of the educational process with the help of a computer ;
- educational material presented and implemented with the help of a computer ;
- a student how and with what means to control knowledge , assess the level of strengthening of skills and qualifications ;
- what kind of information technologies should be used for the implementation of pedagogical and didactic tasks [12] .

When transferring the course to the computer technology of education, the teacher should not only have an idea about the field of science , but also have the skills to systematize knowledge, use teaching methods correctly, and have a good knowledge of the possibilities of information technology. must have imagination . In addition, it is necessary to be aware of the technical tools and software available in creating practical software and accompanying the learning process [13].

Teaching students today using digital technologies v a several types of computer programs are used in teaching. These are primarily test-type control programs, training programs, control and training programs, multimedia encyclopedias , interactive multimedia textbooks. and others .

visual material, video materials and electronic teaching-methodical tools in the teaching of technical subjects are determined by the possibilities that allow to present the educational material with a high level of accuracy [14].

In particular, in the modeling of mechanical and other processes, fundamental learning questions are used in educational presentations accompanied by clear signs that help to strengthen the emotional background of education:

1. increase students' motivation;
2. expansion of opportunities for individualization of education;
3. providing a wide range of communication with students;
4. providing a wide space for active independent activity of students.

Today, it is possible to formulate some tasks that arise from the demand for educational informatization [15]:

First of all, information becomes a decisive factor due to the acquisition of a complex of knowledge, skills and abilities of a graduate of a technical university, the development of personal characteristics that ensure successful performance of professional tasks and comfortable functioning in the information society, and due to high labor efficiency.

Secondly, to improve the teaching technologies used in technical higher education today, to increase the level of training of specialists through the wide introduction of electronic educational tools and technologies into the educational process.

The main task of using modern information technology is to expand the intellectual capabilities of a person. Currently, the concept of " learning " is changing , that is, the use of information in the acquisition of knowledge , its reception and transmission using various telecommunication systems , etc.

The use of digital technologies in modern education is a completely natural phenomenon. Multimedia creates positive moments that contribute to the perception and memorization of the material, including the intuitive reactions of the student, that is, in each lecture of the course, before the task is summarized or given, the student can perform it with a specific voice or tone of a certain type. is work. This course is provided with necessary information in advance and does not require the teacher's attention [16].

Educational tool - interactive multimedia textbooks individualize the educational process more effectively, shorten the study time. Materials in such textbooks are presented taking into account the specific characteristics of the student's memory. Presenting information simultaneously in auditory and visual forms makes it easier for the student to remember the given topics, using all the conveniences of the tools provided by the computer. Interactivity, that is, the ability of the student to control the speed and details of learning, the presence of control blocks allows you to check how well the student has mastered the information and, if necessary, work on mistakes. Based on the above, allows you to use these textbooks for independent study.

The necessary elements of such a textbook are [17]:

- voice accompaniment;

visual material accompanying the animation on the screen , technical training manual, speech, music, sounds;

- high-quality graphics or photos drawn by a professional artist [18] ;

Taking into account the chosen theme, animation inserts, films, "live circuits" etc. are selected by the designer based on a single design. There is a pause for student self-study, with the student deciding when to move on to the next frame by clicking "next". The ability to repeat the explanations of the current frame and "go back" several frames depends on the control block, which can appear after each topic or be distributed across the topic in blocks of two or three questions. Failure to check may result in scoring or returning to the frame containing the correct answer [19].

A student can analyze the topic and enter the words of the terms without stopping the study. How "multimedia" this or that program is, i.e. how fully and effectively using multimedia technologies to understand a new topic, whether the use of multimedia technologies at any stage of the educational process, such as independent work and control of the student's knowledge, significantly increases the quality of the final result possible

The introduction of educational presentations and video materials will help the emergence of new educational methods and lesson forms based on electronic means of information processing and transmission. However, despite the variety of technical tools and technologies used in the educational process, it should be noted that the quality of education depends primarily on the excellence of the educational material, the form of its presentation, and the organization of the educational process [20]. .

For example, when developing a model of educational presentations, a number of principles should be followed:

- the slide film and visual material and have special audiovisual tools that control the perception of the material;
- the dynamics of the presentation of the text is determined by the teacher (this happens in advance during the development of the slide film or during the demonstration);
- the slide film offers the student its own logic of learning the material;
- cross-references are allowed.

Therefore, there are many problems in the traditional learning scheme, which are connected with the increasing flow of new information, the complexity of knowledge, and the lack of illustrative material. In such conditions, attention to intensive independent work does not give positive results for some reasons. The emergence of multimedia tools and technologies allows solving these problems. The introduction of electronic teaching-methodical manuals into the educational process not only frees the teacher from the usual tasks of organizing the educational process, but also allows the creation of information and illustrative

materials presented in various forms, i.e. text , graphic, animation, sound and video elements.

In the absence of technical possibilities for visual presentation of materials, the simplest means of visual impact on students are posters, models, and very rarely, special video films. In a comparative analysis, the shortcomings of these tools are obvious and show that the possibilities of modern multimedia educational presentations are objectively wide and meaningful.

The main way to increase the amount of information received is to increase the ability to see. The increasing density of the flow of information forces students to make maximum use of all channels of perception. Therefore, in contrast to the auditory component (the speaker's voice), which may be of secondary importance, the visual component of the theoretical course should be given greater attention. Educational video presentations allow to present the material being learned in the most detailed and detailed way, to divide it into parts with optimal information saturation and visibility, as well as to combine it with the indicated structure. In addition, electronic video presentations allow the use of features that are not available in ordinary posters, such as animation of individual elements, use of video inserts.

multimedia visual aids is very wide, from pictures in textbooks and existing simple posters to self-made photo and video materials. The use of modern technical teaching tools includes the simultaneous use of problem content as a visualization tool, that is, direct teacher-student communication is established. Therefore, for effective study of the course of technical sciences, it is necessary to use specialized auditoriums equipped with sets of information-control technical educational tools. With the application and use of these tools, it is important to develop a variety of multimedia learning materials and sets for all topics of the course to help students understand the essence of the topic and find ways to solve it.

Teachers of technical universities have the right to choose teaching methods and techniques, and they are given the right to use technical subjects developed by

leading universities and approved by the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. basic study materials are recommended [21].

characterized by their individual approach to each student . Now, with the use of computer networks and online tools, teachers have the ability to provide technical training guides and new information tailored to the individual needs of each student . In the library of the educational institution, there is a systematically organized set of educational resources aimed at meeting educational needs, including full-text educational and multimedia guides, including various presentations, developed in the form of courses on subjects depending on the number of students. There should be interactive electronic textbooks. In the process of self-sufficiency, students should use these educational resources, the development of which will help students to be actively involved in the learning process.

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